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TOOTHACHE AND PECULIARITIES OF DENTAL TREATMENT IN DIFFERENT TRIMESTERS OF PREGNANCY

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ANNOTATION

During pregnancy, many women face toothache. Taking medicines and many medical manipulations during this period are limited, pregnancy is accompanied by hormonal restructuring, which can lead to exhaustion of the organism. Even women who pay careful attention to oral care may experience pain during pregnancy. Hidden dental problems that have not caused problems for years can become active during this period.

Keywords: toothache, pregnancy, women, hormonal changes

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ЗУБНАЯ БОЛЬ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЗУБОВ В РАЗНЫХ ТРИМЕСТРАХ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Во время беременности многие женщины сталкиваются с зубной болью. Прием лекарственных препаратов и многие медицинские манипуляции в этот период ограничены, беременность сопровождается гормональной перестройкой, которая может приводить к истощению организма. С болевыми ощущениями во время беременности могут сталкиваться даже те женщины, которые уделяют тщательное внимание уходу за ротовой полостью. Скрытые проблемы с зубами, которые не доставляли проблем долгие годы, могут активизироваться в этот период.

Ключевые слова: зубная боль, беременность, женщины, гормональная перестройка

Djurabekova Surayyo Tohirovna
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HOMILADORLIKNING TURLI TRIMESTRLARIDA TISH OG'RIG'I VA TISHLARNI DAVOLASH XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Homiladorlik paytida ko'plab ayollar tish og'rig'iga duch kelishadi. Ushbu davrda dori-darmonlarni qabul qilish va ko'plab tibbiy manipulyatsiyalar cheklangan bo'lib, homiladorlik gormonal o'zgarishlar bilan birga keladi, bu esa tananing charchashiga olib kelishi mumkin. Hatto og'izni parvarish qilishga katta e'tibor beradigan ayollar ham homiladorlik paytida og'riqlarga duch kelishlari mumkin. Ko'p yillar davomida muammo tug'dirmagan yashirin tish muammolari bu davrda faollashishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: tish og'rig'i, homiladorlik, ayollar, gormonal o'zgarishlar

Introduction. Toothache is one of the unpleasant sensations in pregnancy. Even those women who pay careful attention to oral care may encounter pain during pregnancy. Hidden dental problems that have not caused problems for years can become active during this period. It is important to know about the fact that you can not tolerate pain in any case! Self-medication during pregnancy can cause harm not only to the mother's body, but also to the child. Women during pregnancy should take medicines only after consulting a doctor. Even habitual and, as it

seems at first glance, painkillers. Therefore, the occurrence of any discomfort and pain is a reason to contact a specialist[1].

An appointment should be made in the event of:

- Painful sensations in the teeth
- Inflammation of the gums (redness, swelling)
- Bad breath
- Increased sensitivity to temperature stimuli
- Bleeding gums
- Purulent discharge

Any carious lesion in the oral cavity is a potential source of infection for the developing foetus. Therefore, if not treated in a timely manner, you can face formidable infectious complications. There are situations when a woman needs emergency dental care. In this case, a woman should seek medical attention in the first hours after the onset of symptoms:

- A fractured tooth
- Cracked or chipped crown
- Damage to the pulp.

A timely visit to the dentist will help to avoid complete tooth loss.

If pregnancy is normal, dental treatment can be carried out at any stage of pregnancy. Preparations for the treatment of dental diseases are selected in such a way as not to harm the health of the child and at the same time to alleviate the condition of the mother. Toothache is an indication for an obligatory visit to the dentist. Pain syndrome is a defence reaction of the organism, which is aimed at making a person notice the problem and take steps to eliminate it. In addition to unpleasant sensations, it provokes the release of hormones into the blood, which can cause undesirable reactions on the part of the foetus[3].

If the pain is a sign of an incipient pathological process, in most cases treatment can be carried out even without radiation (radiological examination) and the use of anaesthesia. Remember that the earlier a pregnant woman goes to the doctor, the greater the chances of saving the tooth without potential risks to the child. Pregnancy becomes a catalyst for pathological processes already present in the body. Caries, gingivitis, periodontitis – all this is exacerbated against the background of vulnerability of a woman's health.

However, there are also causes of toothache, which are provoked by carrying a child.

Such diseases include gingivitis of pregnant women. This inflammatory disease is caused by active hormonal changes and symptoms of toxicosis. As a result, the gums become more susceptible to external influences and the vital activity of pathogenic microorganisms[5].

Toothache while carrying a child can also be due to the growth of the skeleton. If a woman's body does not have enough vitamin D3 and calcium for two, the child begins to 'take' useful substances from the maternal body. As a result, the deficiency of vitamins and minerals leads not only to toothache, but even complete loss of teeth. If women are faced with early toxicosis of pregnancy, the chances of deteriorating dental health increase rapidly. Frequent vomiting leads to a change in the acid-base balance in the oral cavity. Under the influence of acid of gastric juice, the enamel of the teeth begins to deteriorate, and pathogenic microorganisms increase the process of tooth destruction. In addition, early toxicosis of pregnant women is accompanied by nausea and selective eating 98haracte. The woman is forced to choose products not by nutritional value, but irrational attractiveness at a given time. This results in the body not getting all the nutrients and vitamins it needs to stay healthy[2].

Pregnancy is not a contraindication for dental radiography. Modern equipment gives a very low radiation dose, and the woman's body is covered with a special protective apron. Therefore, if indicated, it is not necessary to avoid radiological examination.

- However, if you want to carry out a long planned treatment that requires several radiological examinations, it is better to postpone it until after the birth.

- Pain is a frequent but not obligatory companion of pregnancy. In order to avoid the occurrence of pain during pregnancy. Specialists around the world say that pregnancy must necessarily be planned. A woman's body should be prepared for the upcoming strain. Dental treatment is one of the most important stages of preparation for pregnancy. It is worth treating existing cavities so that you don't have to worry about your oral health during pregnancy.
- After a woman is registered for pregnancy at the antenatal clinic, she is also sent to the doctor for preventive check-ups. Do not ignore visits to a specialist: the dentist will help to identify problems in the early stages and prevent them.
- And in order to save teeth directly during pregnancy, it is necessary:
 - Pay careful attention to oral hygiene
 - Regular brushing, using professional toothpaste and irrigator will help to avoid dental diseases. If you have not yet chosen professional dental care, you should consult a dental hygienist.
 - Complete nutrition
 - A pregnant woman's diet should be balanced. It should contain a sufficient amount of vitamins and minerals, as well as nutritional components.
 - Taking vitamin complexes
 - Unfortunately, eating a full and varied diet is a difficult task. And not always from food a woman can get a sufficient amount of useful substances. In this case, vitamin complexes come to the rescue. Before their use, you should always consult a doctor!
 - Preventive visits to the dentist
 - A dentist will detect diseases at the initial stages and help to get rid of them. Dental treatment at early stages avoids harm to the child's health.
- Contraindications to dental treatment during pregnancy
- There are few contraindications for dental treatment during pregnancy. These include:
 - Threat of termination of pregnancy
 - Risk of premature labour
- In other cases, however, a woman can visit a dental clinic and have dental treatment.
- However, there are a number of procedures that are not recommended for women during pregnancy:
 - Implants
 - In order to perform a quality implantation, several x-rays will need to be taken, which is not recommended during pregnancy. In addition, surgical manipulations may require the use of drugs that are potentially harmful to the foetus. Therefore, it is recommended that a woman postpone the implant procedure until the pregnancy and breastfeeding period is over[3].
 - Professional whitening
 - While carrying a child, the enamel of the teeth becomes more weakened. Therefore, the use of medications can cause even more damage and unpredictable results.

- Placement of fixed dentures

Fixed dentures and implants are the recommended methods of restoring teeth for everyone except pregnant women. Fixation of such structures requires a large volume of medical interventions and affects the emotional state of the woman. Therefore, during pregnancy it is worth giving preference to a removable prosthesis.

Features of dental treatment in different trimesters of pregnancy

In different trimesters during pregnancy, the list of permitted medical manipulations may differ.

The first trimester of pregnancy lasts from conception to the 12th week. This is one of the most important periods of child development, because it is then that the vital organs are laid. But at the same time, the placenta is not yet fully formed, so harmful substances from the outside can disrupt the harmonious development. The period up to 8-9 weeks is characterized by a high risk of spontaneous abortion. And toxicosis does not let the future mother feel well and withstand treatment in the dental chair. Therefore, if it is possible to avoid dental intervention, it is postponed to the second trimester of pregnancy.

The second trimester lasts from 13 to 24 weeks. It is this period that is considered optimal for dental manipulations. The placental barrier is already formed: it reliably protects the developing organism from harmful influences from the outside. The health of the expectant mother allows her to spend a long time in the dental chair. All routine dental treatment procedures

and professional oral hygiene are recommended to be carried out during this period[6].

The third trimester begins from the 25th week of pregnancy and continues until the onset of labour. It is also considered unfavourable for dental manipulations. It's all about the fact that the female body becomes weakened by the course of pregnancy. Many expectant mothers have shortness of breath, a decrease in blood pressure. In a semi-lying position, the weight of the uterus and the fetus squeezes the inferior vena cava, which is also characterized by poor health. A woman's uterus is preparing for labour and reacts more intensely to external stimuli (including medications). Therefore, complex dental interventions in the third trimester are fraught with premature labour [7].

Conclusions: Thus, dental treatment during pregnancy should be painless. However, there are many limitations that lead to difficulties in drug selection. Modern anaesthetics of the latest generation are not able to cross the placental barrier, however, effectively relieve pain.

Treatment of dental diseases without pain and discomfort – it is possible.

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